

The Relationship of Spatial Fisheries Diversity with Hydrological Conditions of Ulhas River Estuary

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***Abstract :** Relationship of qualitative and quantitative fisheries diversity with the environmental variables was studied for the period of two years along the three zones, viz. upper, middle and lower, of the Ulhas River estuary. Total ten hydro-sedimentological parameters were analyzed on monthly basis from each zone to depict ambient pollution level. Zones with comparatively higher pollution level deterred fisheries landings. The principal coordination analysis (PCO) ordination and zonewise K-dominance curves revealed the direct correlation of fish diversity with the existent spatial environmental conditions of the Ulhas River estuary.*

Keywords: hydrological conditions, parameters, water pollution, Ulhas River, estuary, fisheries, diversity, landings, water color, phosphates, nitrates, DO, BOD, organic carbon, silt, principal coordination analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Ulhas River estuary (URE) is an estuarine part of Ulhas River which confluences with several rivers viz. Bharvi, Kalu, Bhatsa etc. while meandering through the hilly terrain of Raigad and Thane districts before it meets the Arabian Sea near historical Vasai fort. The study area extended from 19°14'51"N (Latitude) and 73°06'55" E (Longitude) near kalyan road-bridge to 19°19'18" N and 72°47'21" E at the mouth of the estuary opening to Arabian sea at Paachu jetty near Vasai (Bassein) Fort. Hence URE was also referred as Bassein creek named after Bassein fort.

URE is highly impacted by industrial, urban and certain civil activities viz. textile, medicinal, paint and chemical industries, domestic sewage, mangrove annihilation, solid waste disposal, reclamation etc. along upper reach (UZ-I); agriculture fields, solid waste disposal, sand dredging, bridges, pipelines and mangrove annihilation in middle reach (UZ-II) and sand dredging, boat building, reclamation, bridges in the lower reach (UZ-III). Industries were established along the banks of Ulhas River estuary (URE) at Ambivli, Ulhas Nagar, Kalyan, Dombivli, Thane-Balkum, and Bhayandar on the south bank and Bhiwandi on north bank (Fig.1).

Ulhas River estuary is well known for its hydrological (Metcalf and Eddy, 1979a & 1979b; Zingade, 1979; Durve & Bal, 1961; Patil, 1982; Moghal and Sawant, 1984; Qamrul, 1984; Rathod & Patil, 2009a; Mishra *et al.*, 2007; Lokhande *et al.* 2008; Nikam, *et al.*, 2008b; Menon & Mahajan, 2010), benthos (Mishra, 2002), mangroves (Quadros, 2001; Athalye *et al.* 2003; Nikam, *et al.* 2008a; Borkar *et al.*, 2009; Rathod, 2016), fisheries (Archeivala, 1969; Kunte, 1974; Qamrul and Sawant, 1980; Jyothi & Nair, 1990; Rathod *et al.*, 2002; Quadros and Athalye, 2012, Rathod, 2016) heavy metals and fish biology (Mutsaddi, 1964; Mutsaddi & Bal, 1969 & 1973; Krishnamurti and Nair, 1999; Rathod, 2005; Rathod & Patil, 2009b, Rathod, 2016) studies by various experts. However, the pollution was not correlated with the fishery diversity on qualitative and quantitative basis in earlier studies.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The selection of sampling station was based on the convenience of approachable site for the observation of mudskippers during the ebb tide phase and the occurrence of anthropogenic activities probably causing severe decline in health of water in the vicinity of the sampling station. Also the sampling stations were selected towards the lower side of the zones to ensure that the samples thus collected represented the appropriate hydro-sedimentological characteristics of the study zone.

Hydro-sedimentological parameters were assessed on monthly basis from July 2004 to June, 2006. The samples were collected at their respective sampling stations of three zones of URE viz. **Station-I** at Kharegaon sand landing centre lying in zone one (**UZ-I**, extending from Dombivli-Kalayan to Kasheli-Bhiwandilike bridge); **Station-II** at Gaimukh jetty lying in zone two (**UZ-II**, from Kasheli-Bhiwandi bridge to Versova bridge); and **Station-III** at Bhayandar Ghodbundar a sand landing centre found in zone three (**UZ-III**, from Versova bridge to Bhayandar-Vasai bridge) (Fig.1).

Fig.1: Google map of Ulhas River estuary showing divisions (red lines) of the study zones UZ-I, UZ-II & UZ-III and their corresponding sampling stations (UI, UII & UIII).

Hydrological variables like water color, light penetration and dissolved oxygen (DO) were assessed on site. Water samples were collected during flood-tide in washer-capped PVC bottles of 1.5L capacity from each station separately and carried to laboratory for instant analyses of remaining parameters. Water samples were filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 42 (Ashless; porosity 2.5µm.) before use. Sediment samples were collected by scraping superficial layer at ebb-tide in polyethylene bags and oven dried at 70°C temperature until the constant weight was gained before analyses of soil texture and Organic carbon (Org-C). The hydro-sedimentological parameters were analyzed using following methods (Table 1).

Table-1: The water and sediment parameters

Sr.No.	Hydrological Parameter	Abbreviation	Method of Analysis
1	Water color (FU unit) (Fig. 'A')	WC	Forel-Ule Scale (Prabhakar, 2002; Wernand & Woerd, 2010)
2	Light penetration (LP)	LP (cm)	Secchi disc
3	Suspended solids (SS)	SS (gm/L)	Evaporation method
4	Salinity (ppt/psu) (Sal)	Sal (ppt)	Mohr's argentometric method
5	Dissolved oxygen (DO)	DO (mg/L)	Winkler's method
6	Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)	BOD (mg/L)	Winkler's method
7	Nitrate-nitrogen (NO ₃ -N)	NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	Phenol-disulphonic acid method
8	Phosphate phosphorus (PO ₄ -P)	PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	Ammonium molybdate method
Sr.No.	Sedimentological Parameter	Abbreviation	Method of Analysis
1	Organic carbon	Org-C (%)	Walkley and Black method (1934)
2	Soil texture (silt)	Silt (%)	Buchanan's pipette method (1984)

Data of environmental variables was processed in Primer v6 software to obtain resemblance in Euclidean distance matrix after overall transformation of the samples to fourth-roots and normalizing it. Principal coordination analysis (PCO) ordination was run and overlaid by normalized data of environmental variables. The biological data such as fishery species diversities (abundance and biomass) and diversity indices were run for resemblance in Bray-Curtis similarity matrix after overall transformation to the square-root/fourth-root of the samples (Clarke & Warwick, 2001) before PCO was obtained. The data of fisheries species biomass against abundance was used to produce zone wise K-dominance or ABC (Abundance Biomass Comparison) curves (*Warwick, 1986; SOKI Wiki, 2014).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Hydro-sedimentology

Water colour ranged from 14 FUS to maximum 25 FUS. Despite the negligible sand dredging in UZ-I the WC remained fairly high which portrayed impact of high anthropogenic perturbation. However, high WC levels in UZ-II and UZ-III attributed to the extensive sand dredging activities. Light penetration ranged from 2 cm to 46.25 cm dependent on the seasons and other human activities. LP declined in rainy season due to agricultural field sheet flow and storm water from the urban sectors of Thane, Kalyan, Dombivli, Alimghar, Anjur, Vehale, Bhiwandi, Mumbra, Kharegaon, Kalher, Kevani and Kharbhao areas. Low LP in UZ-II and UZ-III was due to high sand dredging activities whilst in UZ-I it probably depicted repercussions due to the domestic sewage, industrial effluents and certain allochthonous sources like river influx, agricultural fields etc. SS, on an average, ranged from minimum 0.45 gm L⁻¹ to maximum 13.44 gm L⁻¹ (Table 2). Extensive sand dredging in UZ-II attributed to the high levels of SS. UZ-III also had considerable sand dredging activities. But UZ-I was impacted due to the contribution of SS from adjacent human habitation. Low salinity levels (minimum 0.19 ppt) was related to either fresh water influx due to the rains in monsoon season or the water released from dams, intermittently, during non-monsoon months. This probably encouraged the entry of fresh water fish species in UZ-I from riverine part of URE and other rivers confluences like Bhatsa, Kalu, Bharvi etc. Salinity gradually increased towards the oceanic segments of the estuary to maximum of 31.81ppt. DO oscillated from minimum range 0.55 mgL⁻¹ to maximum 4.54 mgL⁻¹. DO remain entirely hypoxic in all the zones. However, UZ-III was, occasionally, enriched with DO probably due to the oceanic tidal water.

Table 2: Hydro-sedimentological parameters of URE (month wise average of two years)

Station	Month	WC	LP	SS	Sal	DO	BOD	PO ₄	NO ₃	Org-C	Silt
UI	JULY-UI	15.00	9.25	0.45	0.19	3.78	2.98	0.33	3.69	2.23	26.54
	AUG-UI	16.00	11.75	2.80	0.56	3.27	5.09	0.39	10.52	2.34	23.70
	SEPT-UI	18.00	5.75	3.90	1.89	0.76	7.58	1.63	1.02	2.14	30.78
	OCT-UI	17.00	13.75	3.02	12.04	3.53	12.12	0.20	6.54	2.20	41.97
	NOV-UI	17.00	32.75	3.84	18.14	2.07	8.19	0.15	7.11	2.29	39.85
	DEC-UI	17.00	24.25	8.54	18.28	3.38	4.55	0.18	7.98	2.36	29.90
	JAN-UI	16.00	23.25	6.69	18.24	2.62	10.89	0.22	4.41	2.53	21.61
	FEB-UI	16.00	18.00	4.96	21.89	0.55	4.75	0.42	12.47	2.55	30.40
	MAR-UI	17.00	21.75	12.33	23.91	1.76	6.74	0.49	18.53	2.10	33.95
	APR-UI	17.00	18.75	2.95	22.15	1.36	17.73	0.33	6.04	2.15	27.24
	MAY-UI	14.00	11.00	1.78	25.61	2.77	8.79	0.25	5.00	2.19	38.53
	JUN-UI	25.00	10.75	1.21	18.97	1.11	10.29	0.46	2.81	2.32	30.63
UII	JULY-UII	18.50	12.50	2.00	1.56	4.03	9.30	0.26	2.73	2.06	60.53
	AUG-UII	19.50	5.00	5.40	5.16	3.48	1.41	0.28	4.44	1.99	36.51
	SEPT-UII	20.00	2.00	5.10	10.35	1.16	1.82	0.25	0.62	1.76	45.28
	OCT-UII	15.00	19.00	13.44	20.65	4.18	2.12	0.16	0.83	1.61	42.75
	NOV-UII	18.50	46.25	12.69	20.87	3.42	4.24	0.13	2.30	1.69	46.87
	DEC-UII	16.00	36.00	11.95	21.31	2.87	3.03	0.13	2.91	1.80	44.43
	JAN-UII	19.50	8.00	4.92	25.58	2.82	6.52	0.22	3.48	1.22	45.19
	FEB-UII	19.50	13.25	3.98	27.91	0.96	6.51	0.40	12.20	1.37	55.17
	MAR-UII	19.50	8.25	10.01	26.30	1.18	19.65	0.41	17.30	1.70	44.06
	APR-UII	19.50	14.50	3.52	27.25	1.16	4.81	0.49	4.31	2.26	58.20
	MAY-UII	17.50	20.25	0.71	31.46	1.56	3.18	0.34	4.74	1.54	52.89
	JUN-UII	18.50	20.00	1.04	25.47	2.17	4.99	0.33	3.59	1.61	43.14
UIII	JULY-UIII	15.00	12.50	2.30	3.13	4.54	0.96	0.45	5.63	2.15	46.13
	AUG-UIII	19.50	5.00	4.90	11.55	2.07	2.47	0.30	6.83	1.97	47.93
	SEPT-UIII	21.00	2.75	6.90	14.71	1.91	2.12	0.80	2.55	1.86	44.62
	OCT-UIII	14.50	20.25	8.81	22.77	3.93	3.03	0.13	0.88	1.75	40.45
	NOV-UIII	18.50	29.00	12.92	23.10	2.47	2.73	0.16	3.32	1.52	38.53
	DEC-UIII	16.00	21.25	3.46	24.15	4.13	2.63	0.24	2.82	1.57	48.87
	JAN-UIII	18.00	11.50	3.96	27.04	3.07	9.67	0.25	2.32	1.90	37.25
	FEB-UIII	19.00	7.50	0.45	30.64	1.11	21.94	0.27	7.86	1.08	53.35
	MAR-UIII	18.50	8.25	3.81	30.83	2.08	12.06	0.30	15.17	1.09	56.27
	APR-UIII	19.00	11.75	0.63	28.38	2.08	13.49	0.27	4.29	1.54	48.41
	MAY-UIII	21.00	15.00	0.68	31.81	2.37	4.24	0.34	4.18	1.46	50.38
	JUN-UIII	18.50	18.25	1.23	28.97	2.72	5.74	0.35	2.99	1.92	39.64
Overall	Min	14.00	2.00	0.45	0.19	0.55	0.96	0.13	0.62	1.08	21.61
	Max	25.00	46.25	13.44	31.81	4.54	21.94	1.63	18.53	2.55	60.53
	Mean	17.92	15.81	4.92	19.52	2.46	6.90	0.34	5.68	1.88	41.72

Fig.2 : Hydro-sedimentological parameters of URE with reference line (in red) showing standard limits

Persistent hypoxia along with high BOD, phosphates, nitrates, organic carbon and silt levels discerned high organic load in the entire stretch of the estuary. Nonetheless, hydro-sedimentological parameters showed declined condition as the ambient hydrological parameters like dissolved oxygen (DO), Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), phosphates (PO₄-P), nitrates (NO₃-N), organic carbon (Org-C) and silt were frequently recorded beyond standard limits (Fig. 2) of **surface water category-II** (SW-II) as per the guidelines as follows-

Table 3: Standard limits of water/sediment parameters ascribed by various experts

Sr. no	Authors	Parameter/s	Std. limit
1	Ryther & Dunstan (1971)	PO ₄ -P	0.086 mg L ⁻¹
2	Raman & Ganapati (1986)	NO ₃ -N	1.26 mg L ⁻¹
3	CPCB (1998)	DO & BOD	DO, 4 mg L ⁻¹ BOD 3 mg L ⁻¹
4	Athalye <i>et al.</i> (2001),	SS	1 gm L ⁻¹
5	Rathod (2016)	WC and Silt	WC, 10 FUS; Silt, 35%

Zone wise average	Zone	WC	LP	SS	Sal	DO	BOD	PO ₄	NO ₃	Org-C	Silt
	UZ-I	<u>18.21[§]</u>	16.75	<u>4.37[†]</u>	15.15	<u>2.25[∞]</u>	<u>8.31[∞]</u>	<u>0.42[*]</u>	<u>7.17^ψ</u>	<u>2.28^ψ</u>	31.32
	UZ-II	<u>18.17[§]</u>	17.08	<u>6.23[†]</u>	20.32	<u>2.41[∞]</u>	5.63	<u>0.28[*]</u>	<u>4.95^ψ</u>	<u>1.72^ψ</u>	<u>47.99[§]</u>
	UZ-III	<u>17.83[§]</u>	13.58	<u>4.17[†]</u>	23.09	<u>2.70[∞]</u>	<u>6.75[∞]</u>	<u>0.32[*]</u>	<u>4.90^ψ</u>	<u>1.65^ψ</u>	<u>46.07[§]</u>

Underlined bold figures indicate the samples represent level beyond the tolerable standard limits as ascribed by ^{}Ryther & Dunstan (1971); ^ψRaman & Ganapati (1986); [∞]CPCB (1998); [†]Athalye *et al.* (2001), [§]Rathod (2016).*

UZ-I exhibited high water colour (WC), BOD, PO₄-P, NO₃-N, Org-C and lowest DO as compared to the remaining two zones. High BOD, phosphates, nitrates and org-C and low DO might be due to nearby human habitations contributing pollution factors in form of agricultural activities, domestic sewage and industrial effluents. However, the others like LP, SS, salinity, and silt were high in UZ-II and UZ-III. The high silt and low LP in UZ-II and UZ-III probably attributed to the overwhelming sand dredging activities occurred during study period (Table 3).

Spatial scenario of environmental variables in PCO represented 100% variation of ordination. It indicated very high impact of BOD, phosphates, nitrates, organic carbons on UZ-I whereas UZ-II and UZ-III were highly impacted due to the sand dredging activities revealing significant variations in DO, silt, suspended solids (SS), light penetration (LP) and water colour (WC). Overall UZ-II and UZ-III were closer in the makeup of environmental variables (Fig. 3).

Fish Species Diversity

URE was represented by total 134 species belonging to 65 families composed of 100 species from 48 families of fin-fish; 25 crustacean species belonging to 12 families and 9 species of molluscs from 5 families. UZ-I was represented by 40; UZ-II by 85 whilst UZ-III by 122 fish species. Total 13 and 12 fresh water fin-fish species were identified from UZ-I and UZ-II respectively. UZ-III was found to be richest in fish species diversity which mostly comprised of marine fish (Fig. 4 and 5).

Fish landings were recorded as 32904 kg in UZ-I; 38280 kg in UZ-II and 53739 kg in UZ-III (Table 4). Similar observation was mentioned by Qamrul and Sawant (1980) in upper zone of URE but it was not correlated with the hydro-sedimentological conditions of the ambient water. The fish species structure was in accordance to the environmental variables which defined that UZ-II and UZ-II were similar in characteristics as compared to UZ-I in present study (Fig. 5).

Table 4.: A spatial pattern of number of fin-fish and shell-fish species and their landings (kg)

Category	UZ-I	UZ-II	UZ-III
1 Elasmobranchs	0	0	3
2 Marine Bony fish	20	52	82
3 Fresh water fish	13	12	3
Total of Fin-fishes	33	64	85
4 Crustaceans	5	16	25
5 Molluscs	2	5	9
Total of Shell-fishes	7	21	34
Total fish species	40	85	122
Total fish landing (kg)	33112	37852	57973

Fig. 4: Fish species diversity in terms of the species richness and biomass (kg) landings on zonal basis in URE

Fig. 5: PCO ordination of spatial fish species abundance structure represented by 100% of variations depicted low species richness in UZ-I as compared to remaining two zones of URE. Superimposition of the dendrogram obtained from group average mode agglomeration showed that all the three zones had 40% of similarity but UZ-II and UZ-III exhibited closer relation (60% similarity) in species structure (each number on the plot, i.e. 1 to 134, represents a species observed during the present study).

Fig. 6: K-dominance curves of fish species diversity (biomass vs. abundance) along three zones of URE. Overall all the zones have higher biomass than abundance show high stress and grossly polluted conditions. UZ-I had species rank below 100; UZ-II nearly 1000 and UZ-III recorded above 1000. Warwick statistic value (W) depicted high pollution stress in upper reach (UZ-I) which decreased towards the mouth of the estuary (UZ-II & UZ-III).

K-dominance or ABC (abundance-biomass curve) curves indicated that the species diversity increased towards the lower zones of the estuary. The high Warwick statistic values indicated high perturbations in upper zone of the URE (Fig. 6). Mishra (2002) also got similar relationship of benthic fauna with instantaneous pollution status of URE.

CONCLUSION:

The month wise water and sediment parameters study depicted high stress in the ambient water body. Frequent occurrence of low values of DO and LP whilst the high values of WC, SS, BOD, PO₄, NO₃, Org-C and silt attributed to the pollution status of entire stretch of the URE. UZ-I was highly stressed due to anthropogenic activities causing pollution and other disturbances in the water conditions as it lies very close to the human habitations like Kalyan, Dombivli, Mumbra, Kharegaon, Thane, some villages and Bhiwandi. These areas were recognized for residential, industrial, agricultural and other anthropogenic activities probably caused depletion in spatial hydro-sedimentological conditions ultimately impacting adversely on the fisheries species diversity regime of UZ-I. However, UZ-II and UZ-II were comparatively better but high siltation and suspended solids.

Oceanic zones were rich in fish abundance and biomass. Both, quantitative and qualitative diversity of fisheries increased from head towards mouth of the URE according to the pollution gradient. Due to fresh water inundations from the catchment of URE, the UZ-I, held significant fresh water fin-fish fauna. Distant relationship in species structure of UZ-I depicted the impact of fresh water inundation from catchment of Ulhas River affecting the salinity which imparts different fish fauna (fresh water fish species) as compared to the more saline water occurring in lower reaches of the estuary.

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